

On Finding Integer Solutions to Non-homogeneous Ternary Bi-quadratic Equation

$$3(x^2 + y^2) - 2xy = 11z^4$$

S.Vidhyalakshmi¹, M.A.Gopalan²

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Mathematics, Shrimati Indira Gandhi College, Affiliated to Bharathidasan University, Trichy-620 002, Tamil Nadu, India.

²Professor, Department of Mathematics, Shrimati Indira Gandhi College, Affiliated to Bharathidasan University, Trichy-620 002, Tamil Nadu, India.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6948654>

Published Date: 01-August-2022

Abstract: This paper concerns with the problem of obtaining non-zero distinct integer solutions to the non-homogeneous ternary bi-quadratic equation $3(x^2 + y^2) - 2xy = 11z^4$. Different sets of integer solutions are illustrated.

Keywords: non-homogeneous bi-quadratic, ternary bi-quadratic integer solutions.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Diophantine equations are rich in variety and offer an unlimited field for research [1-4]. In particular refer [5-28] for a few problems on Biquadratic equation with 3 unknowns. This paper concerns with yet another interesting Biquadratic Diophantine equation with three variables given by $3(x^2 + y^2) - 2xy = 11z^4$ for determining its infinitely many non-zero distinct integral solutions

II. METHOD OF ANALYSIS

The non-homogeneous ternary bi-quadratic equation under consideration is

$$3(x^2 + y^2) - 2xy = 11z^4 \quad (1)$$

Introduction of the linear transformations

$$x = 2(u + v), y = 2(u - v), z = 2w, u \neq v \neq 0 \quad (2)$$

in (1) leads to

$$u^2 + 2v^2 = 11w^4 \quad (3)$$

Solving (3) for u, v, w through different ways as illustrated below and using (2), one

Obtains the corresponding integer solutions to (1).

Way 1:

Let

$$w = a^2 + 2b^2 \quad (4)$$

Write 11 on the R.H.S. of (3) as

$$11 = (3 + i\sqrt{2})(3 - i\sqrt{2}) \quad (5)$$

Substituting (4) & (5) in (3) and employing the method of factorization, consider

$$u + i\sqrt{2}v = (3 + i\sqrt{2})(a + i\sqrt{2}b)^4 \quad (6)$$

On equating the real and imaginary parts in (6), the values of u, v are obtained.

In view of (2), the corresponding integer solutions to (1) are obtained as

$$\begin{aligned} x &= 8(a^4 - 12a^2b^2 + 4b^4) + 2(4a^3b - 8ab^3), \\ y &= 4(a^4 - 12a^2b^2 + 4b^4) - 10(4a^3b - 8ab^3), \\ z &= 2(a^4 + 2b^2) \end{aligned}$$

Note 1:

The integer 11 on the R.H.S. of (3) is also represented as

$$11 = \frac{(7 + i5\sqrt{2})(7 - i5\sqrt{2})}{9}$$

Repetition of the above process leads to a different set of integer solutions to (1).

Way 2:

Rewrite (3) as

$$u^2 + 2v^2 = 11w^4 * 1 \quad (7)$$

Consider 1 on the R.H.S. of (7) as

$$1 = \frac{(1 + i2\sqrt{2})(1 - i2\sqrt{2})}{9} \quad (8)$$

Following the procedure as in Way 1, the corresponding integer solutions to (1) are found to be

$$\begin{aligned} x &= 54(6(a^4 - 12a^2b^2 + 4b^4) - 15(4a^3b - 8ab^3)), \\ y &= 54(-8(a^4 - 12a^2b^2 + 4b^4) - 13(4a^3b - 8ab^3)), \\ z &= 18(a^2 + 2b^2) \end{aligned}$$

Note 2:

The integer 1 on the R.H.S. of (8) is also expressed as

$$1 = \frac{(2r^2 - s^2 + i2\sqrt{2}rs)(2r^2 - s^2 - i2\sqrt{2}rs)}{(2r^2 + s^2)^2}$$

Repeating the above process, a different set of solutions to (1) are obtained.

Way 3:

Express (3) in the form of ratios as

$$\frac{u + 3w^2}{w^2 + v} = \frac{2(w^2 - v)}{u - 3w^2} = \frac{\alpha}{\beta}, \beta \neq 0 \quad (9)$$

Solving the above system of double equations (9), one has

$$u = 3\alpha^2 + 4\alpha\beta - 6\beta^2, v = -\alpha^2 + 6\alpha\beta + 2\beta^2, w = s^2 + 2r^2 \quad (10)$$

where

$$\alpha = 2r^2 - s^2, \beta = 2rs$$

From (10) and (2), the corresponding integer solutions to (1) are given by

$$\begin{aligned} x &= 2(8r^4 + 2s^4 - 24r^2s^2 + 40r^3s - 20rs^3), \\ y &= 2(16r^4 + 4s^4 - 48r^2s^2 - 8r^3s + 4rs^3), \\ z &= 2(2r^2 + s^2) \end{aligned}$$

Note 3:

One may also write (3) in the form of ratios as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{u + 3w^2}{2(w^2 + v)} &= \frac{(w^2 - v)}{u - 3w^2} = \frac{\alpha}{\beta}, \beta \neq 0, \\ \frac{u + 3w^2}{(w^2 - v)} &= \frac{2(w^2 + v)}{u - 3w^2} = \frac{\alpha}{\beta}, \beta \neq 0, \\ \frac{u + 3w^2}{2(w^2 - v)} &= \frac{(w^2 + v)}{u - 3w^2} = \frac{\alpha}{\beta}, \beta \neq 0, \end{aligned}$$

The repetition of the above process gives three more integer solutions to (1).

Way 4:

The substitution of the transformations

$$w^2 = X + 2T, v = X + 11T, u = 3U \quad (11)$$

in (3) leads to

$$X^2 = U^2 + 22T^2 \quad (12)$$

which is satisfied by

$$T = 2rs, U = 22r^2 - s^2, X = 22r^2 + s^2 \quad (13)$$

Substituting (13) in (11), note that

$$u = 3(22r^2 - s^2), v = (22r^2 + s^2 + 22rs) \quad (14)$$

and

$$w^2 = (22r^2 + s^2 + 4rs) \quad (15)$$

Treating (15) as a quadratic in s and solving for s, we have

$$w = (18p^2 + q^2), r = 2pq, s = -4pq \pm (18p^2 - q^2)$$

Using the above values of r,s in (14) and in view of (2), the corresponding two sets of integer solutions to (1) are as presented below:

Set 1:

$$\begin{aligned} x &= 2(-648p^4 - 2q^4 + 216p^2q^2 + 1080p^3q - 60pq^3), \\ y &= 2(-1296p^4 - 4q^4 + 432p^2q^2 - 216p^3q + 12pq^3), \\ z &= 2(18p^2 + q^2) \end{aligned}$$

Set 2:

$$\begin{aligned} x &= 2(-648p^4 - 2q^4 - 136p^2q^2 - 1080p^3q + 60pq^3), \\ y &= 2(-1296p^4 - 4q^4 + 256p^2q^2 + 216p^3q - 12pq^3), \\ z &= 2(18p^2 + q^2) \end{aligned}$$

Way 5:

Represent (12) as the system of double equations as below in Table:1

Table:1-system of double equations

System	I	II	III	IV
X + U	T ²	11T ²	22T	11T
X - U	22	2	T	2T

Solving each of the above system of equations, the corresponding values of X, T, U are obtained.

From (11),the values of u, v, w are found .In view of (2), the corresponding integer solutions to (1) are determined. For brevity ,the integer solutions obtained from each of the above four systems are exhibited as follows:

Solutions from system I:

$$\begin{aligned} x_{n+1} &= 2(8k_{n+1}^2 + 22k_{n+1} - 22), \\ y_{n+1} &= 2(4k_{n+1}^2 - 22k_{n+1} - 44), \\ z_{n+1} &= 9f_n + 6\sqrt{2}g_n \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} k_{n+1} &= 3f_n + \frac{9}{2\sqrt{2}}g_n - 1, \\ f_n &= (3 + 2\sqrt{2})^{n+1} + (3 - 2\sqrt{2})^{n+1}, \\ g_n &= (3 + 2\sqrt{2})^{n+1} - (3 - 2\sqrt{2})^{n+1} \end{aligned}$$

Solutions from system II:

$$x_{n+1} = 2(88k_{n+1}^2 + 22k_{n+1} - 2),$$

$$y_{n+1} = 2(44k_{n+1}^2 - 22k_{n+1} - 4),$$

$$z_{n+1} = \frac{1}{2}f_n + \frac{1}{\sqrt{22}}g_n$$

where

$$k_{n+1} = \frac{1}{22}\left(f_n + \frac{11}{\sqrt{22}}g_n - 2\right),$$

$$f_n = (197 + 42\sqrt{22})^{n+1} + (197 - 42\sqrt{22})^{n+1},$$

$$g_n = (197 + 42\sqrt{22})^{n+1} - (197 - 42\sqrt{22})^{n+1}$$

Solutions from system III:

$$x = 216 * 27k^2, y = 36 * 27k^2, z = 54k$$

Solutions from system IV:

$$x = 124 * 17k^2, y = -16 * 17k^2, z = 68k$$

III. CONCLUSION

An attempt has been made to obtain non-zero distinct integer solutions to the non-homogeneous bi-quadratic diophantine equation with three unknowns given by $xz(x - z) = y^4$. One may search for other sets of integer solutions to the considered equation as well as other choices of the fourth degree diophantine equations with multi-variables

REFERENCES

- [1] L.J. Mordell, Diophantine Equations, Academic press, New York, 1969.
- [2] R.D. Carmichael, The Theory of numbers and Diophantine Analysis, Dover publications, New York, 1959.
- [3] L.E. Dickson, History of theory of Numbers, Diophantine Analysis, Vol.2, Dover publications, New York, 2005.
- [4] S.G. Telang, Number Theory, Tata Mc Graw Hill publishing company, New Delhi, 1996.
- [5] M.A.Gopalan, and G. Janaki, Integral solutions of ternary quartic equation $x^2 - y^2 + xy = z^4$, Impact J. Sci. Tech, 2(2), Pp 71-76, 2008.
- [6] M.A.Gopalan, and V. Pandichelvi, On ternary biquadratic diophantine equation $x^2 + ky^3 = z^4$, Pacific- Asian Journal of Mathematics, Volume 2, No.1-2, Pp 57-62, 2008.
- [7] M.A.Gopalan, A.Vijayasankar and Manju Somanath, Integral solutions of $x^2 - y^2 = z^4$, Impact J. Sci. Tech., 2(4), Pp 149-157, 2008.
- [8] M.A.Gopalan, and G.Janaki, Observation on $2(x^2 - y^2) + 4xy = z^4$, Acta Ciencia Indica, Volume XXXVM, No.2, Pp 445-448, 2009.
- [9] M.A.Gopalan, and R. Anbuselvi, Integral solutions of binary quartic equation $x^3 + y^3 = (x - y)^4$, Reflections des ERA-JMS, Volume 4, Issue 3, Pp 271-280, 2009.

- [10] M.A.Gopalan, Manjusomanath and N. Vanitha, Integral solutions of $x^2 + xy + y^2 = (k^2 + 3)^n z^4$, Pure and Applied Mathematical Sciences, Volume LXIX, No.(1-2), Pp 149-152, 2009.
- [11] M.A.Gopalan, and G.Sangeetha, Integral solutions of ternary biquadratic equation $(x^2 - y^2) + 2xy = z^4$, Antartica J.Math., 7(1), Pp 95-101, 2010.
- [12] M.A.Gopalan and A.Vijayashankar, Integral solutions of ternary biquadratic equation $x^2 + 3y^2 = z^4$, Impact.J.Sci.Tech., Volume 4, No.3, Pp 47-51, 2010.
- [13] M.A.Gopalan and G. Janaki, Observations on $3(x^2 - y^2) + 9xy = z^4$, Antartica J.Math., 7(2), Pp 239-245, 2010.
- [14] M.A. Gopalan, S. Vidhyalakshmi, S. Devibala, Ternary bi-quadratic Diophantine equation $2^{4n+3}(x^3 - y^3) = z^4$, Impact J. Sci. Tech, Vol.4(3), 57-60, 2010.
- [15] M.A. Gopalan, G. Sangeetha, Integral solutions of ternary non-homogeneous bi-quadratic equation $x^4 + x^2 + y^2 - y = z^2 + z$, Acta Ciencia Indica, Vol. XXXVIIM, No.4, 799-803, 2011.
- [16] M.A. Gopalan, S. Vidhyalakshmi, G. Sumathi, Integral solutions of ternary bi-quadratic non-homogeneous equation $(\alpha + 1)(x^2 + y^2) + (2\alpha + 1)xy = z^4$, JARCE, Vol.6(2), 97-98, July-December 2012.
- [17] M.A. Gopalan, G. Sumathi, S. Vidhyalakshmi, Integral solutions of ternary non-homogeneous bi-quadratic equation $(2k + 1)(x^2 + y^2 + xy) = z^4$, Indian Journal of Engineering, Vol.1(1), 37-39, 2012.
- [18] Manju Somanath, G.Sangeetha, and M.A.Gopalan, Integral solutions of a biquadratic equation $xy + (k^2 + 1)z^2 = 5w^4$, PAJM, Volume 1, Pp 185-190, 2012.
- [19] M.A. Gopalan, G. Sumathi, S. Vidhyalakshmi, On the ternary bi-quadratic non-homogeneous equation $x^2 + ny^3 = z^4$, Cayley J.Math, Vol.2(2), 169-174, 2013.
- [20] M.A.Gopalan , V.Geetha , (2013), Integral solutions of ternary biquadratic equation $x^2 + 13y^2 = z^4$, IJLRST, Vol 2, issue2, 59-61
- [21] M.A.Gopalan ,S. Vidhyalakshmi ,A. Kavitha , (2013), Integral points on the biquadratic equation $(x + y + z)^3 = z^2(3xy - x^2 - y^2)$, IJMSEA, Vol 7, No.1, 81-84
- [22] A. Vijayasankar, M.A. Gopalan, V. Kiruthika, On the bi-quadratic Diophantine equation with three unknowns $7(x^2 - y^2) + x + y = 8z^4$, International Journal of Advanced Scientific and Technical Research, Issue 8, Volume 1, 52-57, January-February 2018.
- [23] Shreemathi Adiga, N. Anusheela, M.A. Gopalan, Non-Homogeneous Bi-Quadratic Equation With Three Unknowns $x + 3xy + y = z$, Vol.7, Issue.8, Version -3, pp.26-29, 2018
- [24] S. Vidhyalakshmi, M.A. Gopalan, S. Aarthi Thangam and Ozer, O., On ternary biquadratic diophantine equation $11(x^2 - y^2) + 3(x + y) = 10z^4$, NNTDM, Volume 25, No.3, Pp 65-71, 2019.
- [25] A. Vijayasankar, Sharadha Kumar, M.A. Gopalan, "A Search For Integer Solutions To Ternary Bi-Quadratic Equation $(a + 1)(x^2 + y^2) - (2a + 1)xy = [p^2 + (4a + 3)q^2] z^4$ ", EPRA(IJMR), 5(12), Pp: 26-32, December 2019.
- [26] A. Vijayasankar, Sharadha Kumar, M.A. Gopalan, "On Non-Homogeneous Ternary Bi-Quadratic Equation $x^2 + 7xy + y^2 = z^4$ ", Compliance Engineering Journal, 11(3), Pp:111-114, 2020.
- [27] S. Vidhyalakshmi, M.A. Gopalan, On The Non-Homogeneous Ternary Bi-quadratic Equation $xz(x + z) = 2y^4$, IJRPR, Vol.3, Issue7, pp.3465-3469, 2022
- [28] S. Vidhyalakshmi, M.A. Gopalan, On The Non-Homogeneous Ternary Bi-quadratic Equation $8xz(x + z) = 15y^4$, IRJMETS, Vol.4, Issue7, pp.3623-3625, 2022